

PREVENTABLE: an European study on cost-effectiveness of prevention in rare tumour risk syndromes

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ABSTRACT

Importance: The PREVENTABLE project, funded by Horizon Europe (Grant number 101095483), was created to assess the clinical, social and financial impact of applying multidisciplinary and specialized care to prevent advanced disease in families suffering from Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS). The goal is to bridge the knowledge gap on the cost-effectiveness and clinical outcomes of prevention *versus* treatment in these syndromes, and contribute to a better awareness and informed decision-making for patients, healthcare professionals and policymakers.

Observations: RTRS are rare diseases (≤ 5 per 10.000 people) caused by heritable genetic variants that confer a lifetime risk of developing cancers, as high as 100%. In most instances, RTRS patients have a 50% chance of transmitting the disease risk to their offspring, provided they survive childhood or early onset cancers, and reach reproductive age. Due to their complexity, these syndromes pose significant challenges to healthcare systems, leaving many patients underserved. Despite the evidence that intensive surveillance, prophylactic and risk-reduction surgery of healthy RTRS carriers are effective in preventing advanced cancer, most healthcare organizations still prioritize treatment of symptomatic patients. Thus, it is urgent to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of prevention in RTRS.

Conclusions and relevance: A consortium of 16 partner institutions from nine European countries is using an unprecedented approach that merges specialized clinical knowledge on RTRS, real-life clinical data and professionals' expertise and patients' experiences, with health economic models and social sciences. This approach is being used to estimate the cost-effectiveness of surveillance programs and risk-reduction interventions in RTRS, and to delineate guidelines for communication between clinical teams and patients. Our ambition is to demonstrate social and/or financial benefits of prevention, for patients,

healthcare providers and society in general. This special communication presents the PREVENTABLE project rationale and expected impact.

Glossary of terms as used along this manuscript

Germline variant – genetic variation in a reproductive cell that is inherited by the offspring, becoming integrated into the DNA of every cell of the offspring's body;

Cancer prevention – actions undertaken to reduce the risk of developing cancer, including surveillance, prophylactic surgeries and risk-reduction interventions;

Prophylactic surgery – surgical procedure to remove an organ where no clinical findings were detected during surveillance, with the goal of removing organs at high risk of cancer;

Surveillance – monitorization of a patient's organs, systems or conditions without intent of treatment;

Risk-reduction intervention – surgical procedure to remove an organ where clinical findings were detected during surveillance, or a pre-malignant lesion, with the goal of reducing the risk of developing advanced cancer.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare systems play a central role in modern societies by monitoring, maintaining and improving peoples' health ¹. These systems must ensure equitable access to sustainable, high-quality healthcare services for all citizens. To achieve this, it is crucial to develop and implement cost-effective, people-centred solutions that prioritize population health, strengthen healthcare resilience, and support evidence-based policies. This is particularly challenging for rare and complex diseases, including Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS), where the limited patient number and knowledge often hinders effective care ². RTRS Patients often encounter barriers to access necessary care and may

experience considerable delays in receiving an accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment ^{2, 3}. In 2017, these challenges were acknowledged by the European Commission, which launched the European Reference Network (ERN) on Genetic Tumour Risk Syndromes (GENTURIS), with the aim to improve the identification, genetic diagnostics, cancer prevention and treatment of European patients with a genetic predisposition for cancer ².

RTRS are hereditary cancer syndromes caused by heritable pathogenic variants (see glossary) in one or more genes, resulting in genetic predisposition to certain types of benign or malignant tumours. RTRS affect 5 per 10.000 people or less, who often develop cancer at an early age ⁴. A RTRS patient has a lifetime risk to develop one or various cancers that can be as high as 100%. Since many RTRS are inherited in an autosomal-dominant way, patients have frequently a 50% likelihood of transmitting the genetic predisposition to their offspring. When undiagnosed or not surveilled, RTRS patients silently develop advanced cancer, often dying prematurely, and severely impacting theirs and their families' health and wellbeing ^{5, 6}. Asymptomatic RTRS patients which are intensively surveilled or undergo surgical removal of cancer-prone organs, prior to disease development, have a favourable prognosis². In addition, removal or treatment of early-stage cancer or pre-malignant lesions (e.g. colorectal polyps) also translate into survival and quality of life benefit ². RTRS are therefore a unique and tangible context for cancer prevention, early diagnosis and treatment with curative intent. However, preventive strategies, including surveillance, prophylactic surgeries and risk-reduction interventions, are not always prioritized in genetically diagnosed RTRS patients, while they are asymptomatic. Indeed, most healthcare systems keep on opting for treatment of clinically expressed cancer, even when a genetic diagnosis has been made. Even if strongly recommended in national or international high-level guidelines ², preventive

measures in RTRS patients may not be part of the regular healthcare service and reimbursement by insurance companies ⁷. This occurs despite the knowledge that hospitalization has the highest weight on advanced cancer healthcare spending ⁸. It is, therefore, urgent to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of applying preventive measures in RTRS.

To address this medical and economic burden, the research project “Cancer prevention vs cancer treatment: The rare tumour risk syndromes battle” (PREVENTABLE; no. 101095483), funded by Horizon Europe, was initiated. PREVENTABLE is an unprecedented effort that merges specialized clinical knowledge on RTRS pathways of care, real patients’ clinical data and professionals and patients’ expertise, with health economic models and social sciences. The goal is to estimate the cost-effectiveness of preventive interventions in RTRS, and delineate guidelines for its communication among clinical teams and patients. These goals are being achieved by outlining RTRS condition-specific pathways of care and individual patient’s trajectories, identifying the respective healthcare costs, estimating the disease outcomes and modelling disease onset and progression. In parallel, a behavioural analysis is being performed to identify the factors that influence the choice and uptake of care pathways by RTRS patients and clinical teams. PREVENTABLE is also contributing to increase RTRS visibility and awareness through the production of novel educational materials and dissemination of findings to a diversity of stakeholders, including patients and their families, healthcare professionals and policymakers (Figure 1). These outputs can only be successfully achieved through synergistic efforts of multidisciplinary teams, that in the case of PREVENTABLE, comprise 16 partner institutions across nine European countries.

PREVENTABLE’s ambition is to provide evidence that identifying and closely monitoring asymptomatic carriers of RTRS, while offering prophylactic and/or risk-

reduction approaches for organs prone to be affected with cancer, can reduce the number of patients developing advanced disease, improve their clinical outcomes and decreased healthcare costs. Thus, PREVENTABLE aligns with the efforts of the European Union towards the development of cost-effective and people-centred evidence-based health-policies and a preventive medicine paradigm.

Figure 1 – PREVENTABLE framework.

1. PREVENTABLE: A COST-EFFECTIVENESS STUDY BASED ON REAL CLINICAL DATA

Healthcare costs are a concern for the sustainability of health systems in both rich and poor countries. The challenge of decision makers in the health area is to balance the growing demand of services with the limited budget of health entities, and the financial constraints of users ⁹. As a result, an increasing number of health-care systems, both public and private, are adopting results from cost-effectiveness analysis as one of the measures to inform decisions on allocation of health-care resources ¹⁰.

One of the limitations of the published health economics studies on cancer risk syndromes, is the lack of acknowledgement of the diversity of cancers and condition-specific care pathways that can be observed in each of these syndromes. Instead, these studies are usually restricted to a specific cancer type ^{11, 12}. In addition, among patients with the same syndrome, gender-specificities exist, the order and/or age at which cancers occur may be completely different, depending on whether they survive a previous cancer. To improve the knowledge on the real costs in RTRS, PREVENTABLE resorts to the extensive expertise of the consortium clinical teams, acquired by following many RTRS families and individuals. Within PREVENTABLE, we are designing parallel condition-specific pathways of care for each and every RTRS, virtually representing all personal trajectories from RTRS patients. These may include more than one cancer and more than one organ being surveilled/affected in the same patient, thus allowing a better prediction of clinical outcomes and accurate allocation of health costs to very specific patients' trajectories. These pathways of care are being further validated and refined using multicentric clinical data, framing the cost-effectiveness analysis through a patient-centred lens (Figure 2). In addition, a dedicated IT tool was developed to allow the systematic registration of clinical data, following rigorous standards of data integrity and

protection. Informed by the extensive expertise of PREVENTABLE clinical teams in RTRS care pathways, the IT tool ensures that retrospective data collected from patients' clinical records is exclusively focused on procedures directly associated with RTRS. All unrelated clinical procedures are excluded, enabling a highly accurate assessment of the financial and clinical impact of RTRS-specific care pathways.

A limitation of current health economic studies on these syndromes is the use of single-source or single-country data, and the use of direct medical costs collected by others and available in the literature, i.e. predictive economical models¹²⁻¹⁴. In contrast, PREVENTABLE uses data from multiple sources, with country-specific prices per syndrome to allow direct comparisons of clinical care, rather than compare asymmetric healthcare costs across countries. It then automates the price indexing to clinical data from each RTRS pathways of care, facilitating the comparison of prevention-related and treatment-related care pathways, within each syndrome, and subsequent cost-effectiveness analysis.

Figure 2 – The PREVENTABLE patient-centred dimensions: PREVENTABLE employs an innovative approach that integrates specialized clinical expertise on RTRS care pathways, real patient clinical data, and health economic models to generate patient-centered cost-effectiveness data. Additionally, it incorporates social sciences to develop guidelines for effective communication between clinical teams and RTRS patients, while also raising awareness about RTRS. *Created in Biorender.*

2. CONSORTIUM SYNERGY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY AND INTEGRATED APPROACH

PREVENTABLE implements a novel approach to incentivize participation among and with clinical team members. Recognizing the pivotal role of health professionals in driving research initiatives, the project offers financial compensation to ensure their active involvement. By directly tying pay progression to contributions in the project, PREVENTABLE not only acknowledges the importance of healthcare professionals' engagement, but also aligns incentives with research efforts¹⁵⁻¹⁷. This strategic approach not only fosters a sense of value and recognition among healthcare professionals, but also serves to enhance their motivation, thereby catalysing their commitment to the project's objectives. In doing so, PREVENTABLE underscores the significance of incentivization in cultivating a conducive environment for research engagement within healthcare settings, ultimately leading to improved patient care and outcomes.

Another example of PREVENTABLE's comprehensive and integrated approach is the active involvement of Information Technology (IT) teams in the development of a specialized tool for data collection. Unlike their traditional role of providing technical support, these teams are directly contributing to the study by creating a platform that standardizes the gathering of real patient data across all partners and countries involved in the project. This ensures consistency and reliability in data integration and analysis,

fostering collaboration and enabling robust evidence-based insights. By engaging IT teams as integral participants in the research process, PREVENTABLE underscores the value of cross-disciplinary contributions in driving innovation and advancing patient-centred outcomes.

Moreover, the project emphasizes multidisciplinary transversality, engaging professionals from diverse fields such as healthcare, basic research, health economics, social sciences, and patient advocacy. This inclusive approach highlights the necessity of collective expertise to address the complex challenges posed by RTRS, comprehensively and effectively. Clinical members play a pivotal role by contributing with their specialized knowledge of these syndromes and providing real patient data, ensuring that research remains grounded in practical, real-world insights.

Interoperability is another key focus of the project. By integrating expertise and data across partners, PREVENTABLE establishes a robust network that facilitates the sharing of clinical insights and best practices. This is further supported by stakeholder mapping and the development of RTRS educational materials, designed specifically to help at-risk individuals in complex decision-making processes, to inform general physicians on risk criteria, clinical presentations and outcomes, and preventive options, and to aid decision-makers in better policies and management of these complex syndromes. Through this interdisciplinary collaboration and innovative approaches to communication and education, PREVENTABLE is advancing cost-effective preventive care strategies, while striving to improve RTRS patient visibility and outcomes across Europe.

3. PREVENTABLE IMPACT AND EXPECTED OUTPUTS

PREVENTABLE aims to fundamentally transform the healthcare landscape for RTRS, by offering innovative tools and approaches to estimate the real health costs of prevention

versus treatment. Central to this effort is the development of parallel condition-specific pathways of care for each RTRS, which reflect the diverse disease trajectories and clinical needs of each patient, and across patients. These pathways will be validated and consolidated using a collaborative cohort of 1.967 RTRS carriers and 2.026 non-carriers of RTRS causative variants, from a total of 1.108 families, followed in nine European reference centres. This unprecedentedly large cohort and wide range of clinical trajectories will enable a robust comparison of cost-effectiveness models, providing invaluable resources for decision-makers and policymakers in healthcare.

3.1 Social and economic impact

Ten percent of all diagnosed cancers are predicted to be heritable, affecting 1.35 million European adults and children, leading to healthcare spending of approximately €20 billion in 2020, only for tumour risk syndromes (hereditary cancer syndromes)¹⁸. This accounts for one-tenth of the estimated total cost of cancer. Preventing cancer in blood relatives of RTRS carrier patients, identified through predictive genetic testing, can significantly reduce treatment costs. In addition, a negative result in the genetic test of individuals from RTRS families allows their discharge from the healthcare system, thus reducing the expenses associated with unnecessary lifelong surveillance.

By focusing on early intervention and preventive care for at-risk individuals, the project anticipates substantial reductions in healthcare expenditure by preventing the need for costly treatments at advanced disease stages. Given that asymptomatic RTRS relatives can be identified early, surveillance and preventive measures can be implemented, before cancer develops, which will lower overall treatment costs. This shift from treatment to prevention is expected to improve life expectancy and quality of life for affected

individuals, fostering healthier aging and reducing the healthcare burden over the long term.

3.2 Cost-effectiveness models and healthcare system optimization

The financial impact of shifting from treatment to prevention strategies in RTRS is expected to optimize resource allocation. Savings generated through intensive surveillance of organs at risk, or timely risk-reduction measures, can be reinvested to improve the healthcare infrastructure, enhance outcomes of pathways of care, and ensure that healthcare professionals are better remunerated and incentivized. ERN GENTURIS centres, known for their specialization in RTRS care, will serve as key sites for implementation and knowledge transfer, ensuring that evidence generated from the project leads to improvements in clinical practices, and policy decisions across Europe. Moreover, the project's cost-effectiveness models will be directly applicable to healthcare systems, allowing stakeholders to make informed decisions on how to best allocate resources. By assessing healthcare spending differences between preventive and treatment measures, PREVENTABLE aims to present evidence-based recommendations that encourage sustainability, while improving patient outcomes.

3.3 Communication guidelines for effective patient and professional engagement

A critical component of PREVENTABLE is the development of communication guidelines to facilitate informed and person-centred decision-making between clinicians and patients. The project will also focus on enhancing communication within healthcare teams, especially regarding the implementation of preventive measures for RTRS. This will help ensure that medical professionals understand the importance of early detection, risk-reduction, prophylaxis, and personalized care approaches. The guidelines will also

cover the gender dimension, addressing how both sex at birth and gender at diagnosis can influence the disease trajectories, and risk profiles of RTRS patients. Furthermore, a deep analysis of the factors influencing decision-making, regarding cancer risk-reduction options among RTRS caring healthcare professionals and RTRS patients, will be a core part of the PREVENTABLE project. This will be conducted through a mixed-methods study (survey and focus group) that will examine the barriers and facilitators to the referral and uptake of risk-reduction and care option, using a behavioural science approach. This includes preferred recommendations by caring clinical teams, patients' preferences and perception of outcomes related to cancer risk, and guidelines for communication in this setting.

3.4 Gender Dimension

PREVENTABLE recognizes the importance of sex and gender in the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of RTRS. Sex differences are defined as biological differences associated with the male *versus* female genotype at birth, whereas gender differences reflect behavioural or socio-cultural distinctions arising from gender identity. Both sex and gender can significantly impact cancer susceptibility, response to treatment, and overall patient outcomes ¹⁹.

Many RTRS demonstrate differential effects in males and females due to biological and genetic differences at birth, as well as the organ-specific nature of these syndromes ^{20, 21}. For example, in Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), caused by defects in the *CDH1* gene, both males and females have a significant risk of gastric cancer. However, females also face an additional risk of developing breast cancer ^{22, 23}. While the genetic diagnosis and prognosis for gastric cancer are similar in both sexes, recommendations for surveillance and risk-reduction measures differ ²².

PREVENTABLE also acknowledges the importance of gender inclusivity in clinical care. Gender dysphoria does not affect cancer risk, but can influence the likelihood of undergoing screening for birth sex organs, which may be further impacted by provider-related factors (e.g., lack of education or comfort with transgender care) and patient-related factors (e.g., exacerbation of gender dysphoria due to physical exams) ²⁴. These challenges highlight the need for adjustments in communication guidelines and recommendations to ensure they are inclusive of gender non-conforming and transgender individuals. The project will use sex and gender inclusivity in pedigree nomenclature to better capture how these factors intersect with genetic predispositions and health outcomes ²⁵. By developing these inclusive tools and guidelines, the PREVENTABLE project aims to ensure that the healthcare needs of all individuals - regardless of their gender identity - are appropriately addressed in the context of cancer prevention and treatment for RTRS.

3.5 Long-term Vision and Dissemination

The long-term goal of PREVENTABLE is to create a sustainable impact by providing actionable knowledge, IT tools, and health economic models that can be scaled beyond the specific RTRS studied. These tools will support healthcare professionals in delivering personalized care, while enabling patients and families to make informed decisions about preventive healthcare. Furthermore, the findings from the project will serve as a blueprint for future initiatives targeting other inherited conditions, contributing to the broader goal of integrating technological innovations into healthcare systems. By focusing on prevention and early detection, the project seeks to shift the healthcare paradigm from a reactive to a proactive, people-centred, and community-based approach, ultimately improving health outcomes and healthcare equity across Europe.

3.6 Addressing the Variety of Stakeholders

For an effective dissemination, PREVENTABLE has identified eight primary target groups, ensuring that its impact extends across various sectors of the healthcare system. These include: i) Patients and Their Families, ii) Hospital Managers, iii) Healthcare Professionals, iv) Policymakers, v) Healthcare Institutions, vi) Patients' Associations, vii) Research and Clinical Team, and viii) Health Economic Experts.

By involving these groups, the project creates a platform for multidisciplinary collaboration, ensuring that all aspects of healthcare - clinical, economic, and social - are addressed. Patients' associations will play a crucial role in raising awareness, advocating for patients' needs, and supporting the communication of prevention strategies to the public.

4. RARE TUMOUR RISK SYNDROMES

PREVENTABLE focuses on eight RTRS that, despite their differences, share common challenges (Figure 3). Cancer development in these syndromes is highly unpredictable - cancers can emerge in various organs, at different ages, and may recur in the same or other organs. Additionally, some cancers exhibit gender-specific patterns, further complicating disease management. In this context, consensus clinical guidelines and the expertise of specialized RTRS clinical teams are essential to ensure timely, effective, and personalized prevention care. The eight RTRS addressed in PREVENTABLE are the following: i) Birt-Hogg Dubé Syndrome (BHDS), ii) Familial Malignant Melanoma (FMM), iii) Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumour Syndrome (GIST), iv) Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), v) Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinomas

(HLRCC), vi) Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (LFS), vii) PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (PHTS), and viii) Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (PJS).

An overview of the key aspects of these RTRS is presented below.

Figure 3 - Clinical and epidemiological information for eight different rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS) addressed in PREVENTABLE. For each syndrome, the causal gene(s), the most commonly cancer-prone organs, and the range of cancer risk are indicated. Organs are depicted at the earliest age of cancer onset associated with that organ in the context of the respective RTRS. *Created in Biorender.*

4.1. The PREVENTABLE Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes

Each of the PREVENTABLE syndrome is associated with pathogenic variants in particular genes, leading to unique cancer risks and clinical manifestations. Proper diagnosis and management of these syndromes rely on genetic testing, regular surveillance, and tailored interventions to reduce cancer-related mortality and improve patient outcomes. Information about the cancer risk, disease manifestations and clinical management strategies for the eight RTRS addressed in preventable is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Phenotypes, cancer risk and clinical management information for the eight different rare tumour risk syndromes addressed in PREVENTABLE.

Syndrome	Key Genes Involved	Phenotype	Cancer Risk	Clinical management	References
Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC)	<i>CDHI</i> , <i>CTNNA1</i>	Diffuse gastric cancer (DGC); Lobular breast cancer (LBC)	DGC: 7%-38% by age 80 (depending on family history); LBC: 37% by age 80	Prophylactic gastrectomy, intensive endoscopic surveillance, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)/ Computed Tomography (CT) for breast cancer, optional risk-reduction mastectomy	22, 26-28
Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumour (GIST)	<i>KIT</i> , <i>SDHB</i> , <i>SDHC</i> , <i>SDHD</i>	Gastrointestinal (GI) sarcomas; Hyperpigmentation; Dysphagia; Parangliomas; Pheochromocytomas	Lifetime risk for GI sarcoma >90% for KIT carriers; SDHx variant carriers have increased risk of paragangliomas and pheochromocytomas	Tumour resection (tumours ≥ 2cm), KIT inhibitors for relapse prevention, regular gastrointestinal surveillance	29
Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (BHDS)	<i>FLCN</i>	Fibrofolliculomas; Lung cysts; Spontaneous pneumothorax; Kidney tumours	Renal cancer: 15%-30% by age 70; Spontaneous pneumothorax risk	Skin lesion treatment, nephron-sparing surgery for kidney tumours, renal MRI every 1-2 years, dermatologic evaluations, and lung monitoring	30-32
Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinoma (HLRCC)	<i>FH</i>	Cutaneous leiomyomas; Uterine fibroids; Aggressive renal tumours	Renal cancer: 15%-19% (lifetime), often metastatic with a poor prognosis	Partial or total nephrectomy, uterine fibroid management, renal MRI from age 8, skin evaluations	33-35
Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (LFS)	<i>TP53</i>	Breast cancer, adrenocortical	Men: ≥70%;	Management of based on lab expertise and	36-38

		carcinoma, osteosarcoma, soft-tissue sarcomas, CNS tumours, other rare tumours	Women: ≥90%; Specific risks include breast (54%), adrenocortical (2%) carcinomas, CNS tumours (6%-19%), soft-tissue sarcomas (15%-22%) osteosarcomas (5-11%)	multidisciplinary team due to genotype/phenotype discrepancies based on type of mutations. Regular whole-body and organ-specific MRI, bilateral mastectomy for breast cancer prevention, neurologic exams, and colonoscopies	
PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (PHTS)	<i>PTEN</i>	Hamartomas; Macrocephaly; Papillomatous papules; Risks for breast, thyroid, kidney, colorectal cancers	Cumulative life risk at 60 years: Breast: 54%-76%; Endometrial: 6%-22%; Thyroid: 10%-23%; Kidney: 3%-9%; Colorectal: 2%-5%; Melanoma: 6%-7%	Thyroid ultrasound every year (from age 10-18), renal ultrasound every 2 years (from age 40), breast screenings (from age 30) with MRI every year and mammography every 2 years; possibly mastectomy, colonoscopies (from age 35-40 years), transvaginal ultrasound for women	39-42
Familial Malignant Melanoma (FMM)	<i>CDKN2A, CDK4</i>	Dysplastic nevi; Multiple melanomas; Pancreatic and breast cancers	Melanomas: 30%-70%; Pancreatic cancer: ~17%	Regular dermatologic exams, sun protection, pancreatic cancer screening for high-risk families	43-48
Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (PJS)	<i>STK11</i>	Gastrointestinal polyps; Perioral mucocutaneous pigmentation; Small bowel, colorectal, gastric, pancreatic, breast, ovarian cancers	Small bowel: 13%; Colorectal: 40%; Gastric: 30%; Pancreatic: 10%-35%; Breast: 30%-50%; Ovarian: 20%; Testicular: 9%	Routine endoscopic surveillance of upper and lower gastrointestinal tract with polypectomy, from age 8, small-bowel surveillance with magnetic resonance enterography / video capsule endoscopy VCE every 1-3 years from age 8, annual pancreatic imaging starting at age 30, regular breast and pelvic exams from age 30, annual examinations for precocious puberty for females from age 8 and annual testicular examinations for males from age 10.	49, 50

4.9 Shared features

All the eight RTRS are associated with a genetic predisposition to develop specific types of cancer. In each case, pathogenic germline variants in specific genes increase the risk

of developing cancer. All of these syndromes are inherited in an autosomal-dominant way, so that a familial clustering is seen in many cases, with a notable percentage of cases exhibiting a hereditary pattern. Individuals with affected family members have a higher likelihood of developing the same condition and, hence, are more likely diagnosed. Most of these syndromes are characterized by an early onset of cancer compared to sporadic cases. Affected individuals may experience cancer at a younger age, making early detection and management crucial. People with these genetic predispositions often face an increased risk of developing multiple types of cancer and multiple primary cancers during lifetime. For example, individuals with Li-Fraumeni Syndrome have a higher risk of developing a wide range of cancers, such as breast cancer, brain tumours, sarcomas, and others. However, certain RTRS are associated with a specific cancer spectrum or histological type. HDGC is associated with an increased risk of diffuse gastric cancer and lobular breast cancer, while BHDS is linked to fibrofolliculomas, lung cysts, and kidney tumours. Some syndromes, like HLRCC, demonstrate high variability in disease severity, even within the same family, leading to different clinical outcomes. The management of these conditions involves regular surveillance and monitoring to detect cancer at an early stage or identify precancerous lesions, allowing for timely interventions. A definitive diagnosis of these conditions is often made through genetic testing, which can identify pathogenic germline variants in specific genes linked to each syndrome. In some cases, prophylactic surgery may be offered as a risk-reduction measure for individuals with high cancer risk, such as prophylactic mastectomy for women with a *TP53*, *CDHI* or *PTEN* pathogenic variant. By recognizing shared features, healthcare professionals can implement appropriate surveillance and management strategies, tailored to each individual's genetic predisposition, ultimately improving outcomes and quality of life for affected individuals.

5. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

PREVENTABLE is expected to generate data covering virtually all possible condition-specific pathways of care for each syndrome, highlighting the most common lifetime clinical trajectories from patients with eight RTRS. The primary objective is to deliver solid scientific and clinical evidence supporting risk-reduction in RTRS. This will include a set of IT tools, cost-effectiveness models, tailored educational materials, and communication guidelines that will enable informed decision-making on preventive healthcare for RTRS by policymakers, hospital administrators, healthcare professionals, and patients.

By promoting health and disease prevention, PREVENTABLE aims to optimize resource allocation, reduce healthcare inequalities, and generate cost savings that can be reinvested to enhance healthcare accessibility. The innovative approach used in this project has the potential to be translated to other inherited diseases. The results of PREVENTABLE will be delivered to a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, to promote the implementation of cost-effective, patient-centered care for RTRS across Europe.

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